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Bachelor's thesis

INTER-ARCHITECTURE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

Transferring parameters between models of different architectures.

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Abstract

Recent years have seen an advancement in parameter transfer techniques that facilitate the exploration of various neural network architectures. Given the experimental nature of machine learning, many architectures must be tested before one can be used in production. As a consequence transfer learning which is intended to improve the performance of target networks on target domains using pre-trained knowledge from related source domain is often used. However, networks based on architectures other than the source one might perform better on the target domain. Ideally we would always utilize target architecture for knowledge transfer but this is not efficient due to the major computationally expensive challenge of pre-training a multitude of neural network architectures. This study introduces and explores the concept of inter-architecture knowledge transfer (IAT) along with some novel computationally inexpensive methods that enable knowledge transfer between different architectures and a simple toolkit implementation of said methods. With the primary objective being speeding up the neural network training from scratch, we demonstrate that IAT from any tested network architecture is superior to Kaiming and Xavier initialization. We also provide neural network architecture similarity measure.

Streszczenie

W ostatnich latach obserwowaliśmy postęp metod służących do transferu wiedzy, które wspomagają eksplorację różnych innych architektur sieci neuronowych. Ze względu na eksperymentalną naturę uczenia maszynowego, wiele architektur musi zostać przetestowanych zanim jakaś zostanie wybrana dla finalnego produktu. W związku z tym często używane jest uczenie transferowe, które ma za zadanie zwiększyć wydajność docelowych modeli użytych w docelowych problemach za pomocą pretrenowanej wiedzy z podobnych problemów. Niestety, sieci bazujące na architekturach innych niż źródłowa mogą działać lepiej dla docelowego problemu. Zawsze wolelibyśmy transferować wiedzę pomiędzy takimi samymi architekturami, ale niestety nie jest to wydajne rozwiązanie w praktyce, ponieważ należałoby pretrenować zbyt wiele architektur. Ta praca ma na celu przedstawić koncept międzyarchitekturowego transferu wiedzy (IAT) wraz z tanimi obliczeniowo metodami, które pozwalają na transfer pomiędzy różnymi architekturami oraz implementację takich metod. Mając na celu przede wszystkim przyspieszenie uczenia sieci od nowa, w badaniach demonstrujemy, że metody przez nas stosowane działają lepiej niż losowa inicjalizacja Kaiming i Xavier. Ponadto, wprowadzamy miarę podobieństwa architektur sieci neuronowych.

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We propose an instantaneous greedy method of transferring knowledge between teacher and student neural networks of different architectures. This computationally inexpensive technique does not require any additional training for the transfer itself. Real-world workflows involve training of a variety of neural networks during the experimentation process. Typically, while conducting the research, minor revisions to the architecture are made on continuous basis to solve the problem. This is done regardless of the research workflow, as multiple hyper-parameters must be tested. Each model is designed by the researcher to improve upon the previous model in some way. With our method, the models retain some of their previous performance and continue to converge further, providing fast feedback.

The primary objective of this paper is to speed up the learning from scratch, if there is no prior pre-trained model. Number of research workflows, such as those often used in Kaggle Competitions with limited resources can be accelerated. The research presented in this work provides experimental validation of the IAT family of operations that was designed to address this problem. Student networks after transferring knowledge from teacher networks - that may be of different architectures or pre-trained on different domains, are more likely to reach convergence faster than the same networks initialized with Xavier/Kaiming methods. Furthermore, we experimentally prove that teacher-student similarity and convergence times are positively correlated.

The major contributions of this work include:

1. Novel approach to transfer learning and initialization.
2. The algorithm for transferring parameters between different architectures via computationally inexpensive transfer technique (one that does not require any additional training) - drop-in replacement for Xavier[GB10] and Kaiming[He+15c] initialization. Proposed algorithm handles almost any architecture transition, unlike parameter remapping methods used widely in neural architecture search [CGS16].
3. No additional assumptions for the problem were used – this is the first universal method to transfer parameters in such a way. Branching is unconstrained.¹
4. Neural network architecture similarity measure.
5. Comparison of similarity between the current SOTA architectures.

¹only when using “Graph Standardization”

1.1 Contribution

Maciej A. Czyzewski	Daniel Nowak	Kamil Piechowiak
Literature analysis		
Running experiments		
Graph standardization	Bipartite matching	Blocks standardization
Argmax matching	Nested bipartite matching	DP matching
Autoencoder score	Magnitude transfer	Clip transfer
Models visualisations	Toolkit design	Trace transfer
Similarity matrix	DevOps management	Distributed training

1.2 Motivation

Due to the experimental nature of machine learning, hyperparameter optimization is necessary. Consider neural network architecture as defined by a set of hyperparameters (number of layers, number of channels, kernel shapes, etc.). Data scientist who tries to apply neural networks to a problem must therefore search the hyperparameter space Ω either manually or using frameworks like Optuna or RayTune. Sometimes, neural architecture search technique is also used, which relies on dedicated search algorithms.

```

1 Define function  $A$ .
2 while stop condition is not met do
3   Next  $v \in \Omega$  is picked;
4   Neural network architecture  $A_v = A(v)$  is created, based on  $v$  and its
   defining function provided by the data scientist;
5   New parameters  $\omega$  are initialized using Xavier (or similar) initialization;
6    $\omega$  are trained using gradient of a loss function  $J$  of the model output
    $J(A_v(\omega, x), y)$ , where  $x$  is the model input and  $y$  is the expected output;
7    $A_v$  and it's parameters are evaluated on a validation subset;
8   Best  $v$  is saved.
9 end

```

Workflow 1: Hyperparameter optimization workflow

To evaluate a vector of hyperparameters v , a model must be trained, which is a time-consuming process. The initialization step can be sped up by using pre-trained weights. Such transfer can be useful for many applications, such as pretraining a set of predefined architectures that can then be used for ordinary transfer learning. Neural Architecture Search techniques might benefit from our computationally inexpensive transfer method, as some of them already use primitive parameter remapping methods. However, to the best of our knowledge,

transferring parameters in the way described by this paper between different architectures is a novel approach and requires further investigation. It is to be expected that transferring parameters between similar architectures should yield better results. Therefore, we also introduce a measure of architecture similarity. Since parameters can't be transferred 1:1 when transferring to tensors of different shapes (at least one smaller), transfer is not trivial. Thus, we propose various heuristic algorithms. In the toolkit section, we also propose a universal architecture - star schema bridge pattern for pluggable algorithm specification.

Figure 1: Demonstration of weight transfer between similar - but different architectures. According to the assumptions of classical transfer learning (parameter mapping), such an operation is not possible (because shapes/keys do not match). Our aim is to make it possible.

1.3 Hypothesis

Given the pre-trained teacher and student models each containing at least one layer of the same type it is possible to transfer teacher's knowledge in such a way as to initialize the student more effectively than with random values without any further training required (assuming teacher performs better than chance).

1.4 Preliminary

This section describes preliminary concepts related to the paper.

1.4.1 Network Architecture

First, we define some hyperparameter space $\Omega \subset R^n$ and hyperparameter vector $v \in \Omega$. Neural network architecture can be considered as $A_v = A(v)$, where $v \in \Omega$ and A is an architecture generating function. Neural network architecture defines what computations model performs given input x and its learnable parameters ω . Model can be thought of as of an instance of a class in sense that it consists of variables (trainable parameters) in memory and refers to some class defining its behaviour given some input. In such comparison, the architecture would be the class.

Since the experiments have focused on computer vision problems that can be solved using Deep Convolutional Network², the following types of trainable layers have been considered:

1. **Dense linear layers** apply the following transformation to the input data:

$$z = W^T \cdot x + b$$

where W is the weight matrix, x is the input and b is the bias.

2. **Convolutional layers** allow for the reduction of the number of layer parameters and can capture spatial patterns. Two dimensional convolutions can be expressed as:

$$Z_{x,y,l} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_c} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n_h} \sum_{j=1}^{n_w} K_{i,j,k,l} X_{x+i-1,y+j-1,k} \right) + b_l$$

where n_h and n_w are height and width of the input, n_c is the number of channels, K is the kernel tensor and b is the bias of the layer.

²known as CNN/DCN

3. **Normalization layers** are used to stabilize the training process by normalizing the data. The most frequently applied normalization layer is Batch Normalization [IS15]:

$$Z_k = \frac{X_k - E(X_k)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(X_k) + \epsilon}} \gamma_k + \beta_k$$

where the γ and β are learnable vectors. The operation is performed independently on every channel.

There are other layers in the CNNs but they do not contain trainable parameters and do not have to be transferred:

1. **Activation functions** are functions used to introduce nonlinearity.
2. **Pooling layers** used to reduce the resolution of the processed data.

1.4.2 Vanishing/Exploding Gradients

When optimizing (i.e. training) parameters using gradient-based techniques, each of the model's weights receives an update that is proportional to the partial derivative of the error function with respect to the current weight in each training iteration. This might eventually cause the model to stop learning when it's error function reaches plateau. One of the exemplary causes of the problem is related to the traditional activation functions used in deep learning. Functions such as sigmoid have gradients of absolute value in range up to 1. Backpropagation algorithm used for fast gradient computation utilizes the chain rule which relies on multiplying many of these small

numbers consequently exponentially reducing the gradient.

One of the ways to resolve this problem is to use activation functions such as ReLU or similar. Another viable solution might be to use residual connections. Contrary, gradients values might reach very high values causing so-called *exploding gradients* when they accumulate. This often happens when activation functions with codomain containing a subset of $(1; \infty)$ are used, or a too high learning rate is applied. To fix the exploding gradients, techniques such as gradient clipping and regularization are used. Clipping limits the gradient values and regularization introduces penalty in loss function proportional to weight's absolute value.

1.4.3 Transfer Learning

Transfer learning is a process of training a network starting from pretrained parameters, i.e. parameters trained using a very similar architecture as usually only some adapter layers are added on top for the new domain. Even though the architectures are not exactly the same because of these layers, it is hard to consider this to be an inter-architecture transfer as the transfer itself is trivial. All layers match easily and their parameters' tensor sizes do not change. Transfer learning gives superior performance to random initialization as similar domains utilize similar features inside networks. Sometimes the term *teacher* is used to describe the source and *student* for the destination model.

1.4.4 Knowledge Distillation

Distillation is the process of transferring knowledge from a large model to a smaller one. Student learns the knowledge by minimizing a loss function in which the target is the output of a softmax function on the teacher model. Well trained teacher model has an output very similar to the ground truth labels. Consequently, the output doesn't contain much more information. To mitigate this, the following class probability function is used:

$$p_i = \frac{e^{\frac{z_i}{T}}}{\sum_j e^{\frac{z_j}{T}}}$$

where z_j is the teacher’s output logit and T is the temperature parameter. With $T = 1$, this constitutes the standard softmax function. However, with the increase of T the probability distribution generated by this function becomes softer. [Geo15] also found that it is beneficial to train the distilled model to produce the correct label. The final loss function was defined as a linear combination of both.

Major downside of this technique is that it is limited to the bigger \rightarrow smaller transfer direction and it requires a lot of computations for the transfer.

1.4.5 Neural Architecture Search

Neural architecture search (NAS) is another approach to the problem usually solved by the workflow 1. NAS can be characterized as a system with three major components: search space, search algorithm and evaluation strategy.

Search space defines a set of operations (layers) and how they can be connected to create an architecture. Since this definition involves human expertise it introduces human bias. This corresponds to A from workflow 1. Search space for NAS can be defined using hierarchical structure to take advantage of the already well-performing network concepts.

Search algorithm heuristically selects the next network architecture candidates, using child model metrics as rewards to optimize candidate generation. This corresponds to a strategy used to pick v from workflow 1.

Evaluation strategy measures or estimates the performance of a number of proposed child models in order to obtain feedback for the search algorithm to learn. Candidate evaluation can be quite expensive, so multiple methods have been proposed to reduce the computational complexity.

NAS reinforcement learning based approaches have recently been introduced and have shown the most promising results. Unfortunately, they are heavily contingent on vast computational resources, making them unsuitable for wide usage. NAS techniques could benefit from our inexpensive transfer method.

The term “parameter remapping” is used in [Fan+20b], their work describes an efficient framework for neural architecture search (FNA++). Their method of transferring weights between different architectures is simple: the weights are transferred by matching layers on depth, width and kernel levels (crop center), which work only between same blocks. Therefore, this method is insufficient for more complex architectures.

There is also Net2Net described in [CGS16] – in their work they present simple method to accelerate the training of larger neural networks by initializing them with parameters from a trained, smaller network. The random mapping algorithm for different layers was done manually. Developing a remapping algorithm would enable the Net2Net technique to be more general. This work further advances knowledge transfer by presenting a better remapping technique that generalises prior methods.

2.1 Weights Initialization

Since using constants such as 0 does not allow for multiple agents (training process is deterministic), there is a necessity for random initialization. Furthermore, when weights are initialized to large values there’s a risk of exploding gradients and likewise small initialization values cause vanishing gradients. Ideally the variance of the inputs of a layer should be equal to the variance of the outputs.

Two of the most prominent algorithms to initialize weights randomly are Xavier ([GB10]) and Kaiming [He+15c].

2.1.1 Xavier

Xavier initialization uses the following normal distribution (second argument is the variance, not standard deviation):

$$N\left(0; \frac{2}{n_i + n_{i+1}}\right)$$

or the uniform distribution version:

$$U\left(-\sqrt{\frac{6}{n_i + n_{i+1}}}; \sqrt{\frac{6}{n_i + n_{i+1}}}\right)$$

where n_i is the fan-in (number of input network connections) and n_{i+1} is the fan-out (number of output network connections). It was observed [GB10] that using this distribution caused dense network to maintain similar variances of weight gradients across layers. $\sigma^2 = \frac{2}{n_i + n_{i+1}}$ helps ensure that the variance of the outputs is roughly equal to the variance of inputs.

2.1.2 Kaiming

However, Xavier initialization approximates the derivative at 0 of the activation function by 1. This does not hold true for rectifier family of popular activation functions that was supposed to further counteract the vanishing gradients problem.

Kaiming [He+15c] derived an initialization method by modeling the nonlinearity of ReLU activation functions. The goal of this method is similar to Xavier's as it utilizes the following variance:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{2}{(1 + a^2) \cdot (n_i)}$$

where n_i is fan-in and a is the negative slope of the rectifier used after this layer (0 for ReLU). Fan-in is sometimes replaced by fan-out because fan-in preserves the magnitude of the variance of the weights in the forward pass (fan-out, likewise, in the backward pass).

Despite the usefulness of the said methods, to the best of our knowledge there has been no well-performing method dedicated to initialization when other pre-trained models of different architectures are available. We use Xavier and Kaiming in our experiments as they make up a good random initialization baseline.

2.2 Generality of layers' features

Important factor in knowledge transfer is whether the parameters in the layers are universal enough to adapt quickly to new information flow.

In [Yos+14] the authors analyze the generality of features present in neural networks at different depths. They train networks on the ImageNet dataset split into two datasets (A and B) and transfer the first n layers of a trained network to the new one (both networks have the same architecture). Then the new network is trained on one of the datasets. They consider four setups - identical source and target datasets with first n layers frozen (BnB), identical datasets without freezing ($BnB+$), different source and target datasets with frozen first n layers (AnB) and different datasets without freezing any layers ($AnB+$).

The performance of the networks with frozen layers drops with n . The neurons in the upper layers have problems co-adapting to the existing ones. In the source network they were learned together and now relearning this relation turns out to be difficult. In case of the BnB network the performance recovers when n almost reaches the total number of layers - relearning one or two layers is easier. The accuracy of the AnB network drops till the end - the source network was trained on a different dataset. It proves that the first layers are general while the subsequent are more specific.

Described behavior does not occur for $AnB+$ and $BnB+$ networks. Because of the fine-tuning, layers can co-adapt. The final performance of the $BnB+$ network stays approximately the same irrespective of n . The accuracy of the $AnB+$ network even grows with n as it uses knowledge from previous domain to generalize better to

the new one.

The paper shows that the order of layers is important. That is why we also preserve the order of layers in some of our methods. Additionally, weights freezing can lead to a drop in performance. Particularly in our case, where not all layers have to be mapped to the target’s layers, we can’t freeze the weights.

2.3 Parameter Sharing

Parameter sharing technique has been proposed in [Pha+18]. It is used to accelerate the architecture search process. The authors design convolutional neural networks consisting of n layers using an LSTM controller network. At each of the n steps the controller chooses one of six different layers: convolution with filter sizes 3x3 or 5x5, depthwise-separable convolution with filter sizes 3x3 or 5x5, max pooling or average pooling. It also creates skip connections deciding which previous layers would be connected with the current one. Then the newly created network is trained and its performance is used to update the controller’s weights using reinforcement learning. Important is the fact that the layers’ parameters are shared between models. They are updated during the training and when a new network is sampled it gets the pre-trained weights. That makes a total of $4n$ trainable layers for a whole NAS process. Thanks to that a new network can use previously inferred knowledge and learn faster. The authors claim that their technique is 1000x less expensive than standard NAS.

Layers chosen for the new model could have been trained in different neural networks. However, after connecting them in a new model they can cooperate to speed up the learning process. That leads to the conclusion that it may be beneficial to arrange layers even though they previously have not been connected.

The paper presents the idea of reusing weights. Nevertheless, they are not transferred to other layers in any way but these are the layers that are used again.

2.4 Parameter Remapping

2.4.1 Net2Net Knowledge Transfer

Net2Net techniques [CGS16] for rapid transferring of the knowledge from one neural network to another were introduced in 2016 and proposed the function-preserving knowledge transfer technique, achieving great performance. The main goal of the Net2Net technique is to accelerate the training of a larger neural net by increasing the size of layers’ tensors (Net2WiderNet) or adding new layers initialized to identity function (Net2DeeperNet). Consequently, this approach is quite limited. Identity function can’t always be used (e.g. bottleneck layers) and it allows for a construction of deeper or layer-wise wider networks ignoring multiple network branching and skip-connections. Net2Net also does not allow for any branching of the network apart from predefined paths.

2.4.2 Path-Level Network Transformation for Efficient Architecture Search

Path-Level Network Transformation for Efficient Architecture Search [Cai+18] (TreeEAS) expands upon reinforcement learning metacontroller techniques for NAS. TreeEAS proposed path-level function-preserving transformation operation that enables topology changes using parameter remapping in NAS. Path-level network transformations allow for a single layer replacement with a multi-branch pattern, not vice-versa.

The proposed path-level operation constructs an equivalent N-branch motif using a convolutional (or others, including depthwise-separable convolution layers [KGC17]) layer - branches mimic the output of the original layer, then they are combined using addition operation and divided by N. Alternatively, branches split the output and then they are concatenated. However, this approach allows just for an one-way replacement. There is no possibility of transferring parameters from one multibranch to another of other type.

2.4.3 Fast Neural Network Adaptation

Parameter remapping techniques based on Net2Net [Fan+20a; Fan+20b] were introduced to NAS. FNA extended Net2Net with the kernel-wise depth scaling. Depth-level remapping adjusts the number of blocks by naively copying the last block multiple times or removing last blocks. Width-level remapping applies a similar operation to number of channels in kernel, removing last channels or creating new ones initialized with zeros. Last dimension considered in FNA, kernel-level is handled with a simple center-clip operation (or centered injection if the weights are transferred from a smaller kernel).

These remapping techniques rely just on copying or clipping, leaving all major Net2Net problems untackled. Branching and skip connections are handled only using manually defined blocks. Wasting data scientist time can be assumed to be just as expensive as a computationally complex algorithm.

2.5 Knowledge Distillation

Knowledge distillation [Gou+20] [Geo15] allows only for transfer in one direction (from larger to smaller network). Transfer itself (distillation) requires the student training process. This causes knowledge distillation to be unsuitable in many applications.

2.6 Network Alignment

One of the major challenges related to our solution was constructing an algorithm for the matching problem - selecting the source and destination layers for transfer methods. This can be interpreted as network alignment problem, i.e. task of identifying corresponding nodes in different networks.

2.6.1 REGAL: Representation Learning-based Graph Alignment

The REGAL [Hei+18b] leverages the K-means algorithm to identify nodes in different networks that portray similar representations between two networks.

XNetMF was devised for node embedding formulation in REGAL. The approach is based on 3 steps. Firstly, structural identity of nodes is computed, then the efficient similarity-based representation is created and lastly nodes are aligned in a similarity matrix. Alignments are the result of arg-max of similarity value in the matrix.

2.6.2 HashAlign: Hash-based Alignment of Multiple Graphs

HashAlign [Hei+18a] was proposed as a hash-based framework for network alignment that leverages structural, edge and node properties. It introduces new LSH techniques and new graph features tailored for network alignment and expresses all alignments in terms of a center graph to mitigate all-pairwise-comparison problem.

Firstly, features are extracted from graph per node, then the center-discovery procedure finds the centre graph and uses hash-based similarity measure for later use in matching.

3.1 Problem analysis

In this study, the goal is to find a way to transfer weights between different architectures, while not requiring the use of a dataset or training scheme (such as in knowledge distillation). In fact, the entire transfer process can be broken down into smaller components as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: The components of a transfer learning strategy. The most effective combination (empirical) is highlighted in green.

Standardization. Ensuring the input of the transfer procedure follows certain layer grouping standard. A block is defined as a group of layers that follow the same information path and are joined together through splits and merges. This step is important both from implementation and logical standpoint since such grouping can facilitate transfer, as shown later in table 1. Ideally basic architecture building blocks should be used as such logical groupings. Nevertheless, exact information about logical groupings may not be easily available at the runtime. Also, blocks defined by the user might not constitute optimal logical groupings, hence the need for automatic standardization.

Scoring. Function that returns a number that indicates the similarity between two tensors or blocks. Similarity matrices required in the matching method are computed using this function between each element of the teacher and the student.

Finding an optimal similarity scoring function using ML models is challenging in absence of feedback. An expert knowledge based scoring system seems rather naive. Thus we assumed that a good score should be given to a pair of tensors of a similar shapes, or ones that match structurally in a given information flow.

Matching. Choose the source and destination layer pairs. Only layers of the same type should be matched with possibly similar shapes. In case when the student architecture contains a subset of the same layers in terms of type and dimension as teacher it is trivial to transfer weights within this subset if the sequence order is kept. Matching algorithms should take into account the fact that even if we find the same layers to transfer to, there’s no guarantee that we can initialize others as identity layers (layers returning input) because of the bottleneck layers with reduced dimensions.

Transfer. Given the matched layer pairs, define the strategy regarding the parameter transfer. The naive transfer method is to clip tensors when transferring to a smaller one or to pad tensors when transferring to a larger one.

3.2 Naive solution

The commonly used approach is to match those weights by names. It won’t work with tensors of different dimensions. Knowledge distillation has a few techniques [Gou+20] [Geo15] that can be used to transfer weights between different tensors. However, these methods are computationally complex and require knowledge transfer from larger models to smaller ones.

3.3 Standardization

Models are implemented in a variety of ways. To be able to transfer weights between different implementations of different architectures, their representations should be consistent. Therefore the first step is to standardize the models into building blocks that represent complex abstract entities that appear repeatedly. A block is defined as a group of layers that follow the same path and are joined together through splits and merges.

Figure 3: Building blocks found in the UNet+ResNet34 [Ni+19] architecture using graph standardization (arrows indicate shortcuts within the block).

3.3.1 Flatten Standardization

The simplest form of standardization is the Flatten Standardization. It converts the model to the list of consecutive layers. Initial layers go first and final layers go last. If there exist parallel paths in the network, their order is determined by the

order in the model’s implementation. This standardization does not preserve logical structures in the network but allows to easily represent all possible models in the same way.

3.3.2 Block Standardization

This method relies on the structure of a model defined by its author in its implementation. Block standardization assigns layers to logical units – blocks. As a result, the representation is two-level. For example, in a ResNet architecture [He+15a] a single building block is composed of: two convolutional layers, two batch normalization layers, two non-linear activation functions and a shortcut connection (adding input to the output). Our method divides a model into such blocks. Every block is represented as a list of layers, while a model is represented as a list of blocks. This two-level approach preserves the network’s structure in more detail.

Separating blocks is not always straightforward. In some cases, there are small sub-blocks inside a block that have to be incorporated into their parent block. An example of such a situation can be seen in the implementation of the EfficientNet-B0 from the *timm library* [Wig19] (figure 5). Each Inverted Residual block contains a Squeeze-and-Excitation block. Basic building blocks of a network are Inverted Residual blocks, so Squeeze-and-Excitation block’s layers have to be included in the representation of an Inverted Residual block (figure 4). Moreover, in this implementation Inverted Residual blocks are grouped. That increases the nesting level. The algorithm has to deal with such difficulties and correctly determine the basic building blocks.

The pseudo-code of the algorithm is present in algorithm 2 listing. The structure of the model makes it possible to consider it as a tree. Each logical component defined by the author has children components, which in the lowest level are layers. Every component is a node in the tree. The algorithm uses a DFS to parse the graph:

- (a) For every component, the DFS returns its content represented as a list containing layers or lists of layers.
- (b) For a node consisting of a single layer, the one-element list with this layer is returned. To prepare a result for compound components, all children nodes are processed at first.
 1. If the depth of the child result is greater than 1 (the returned list contains other lists) or the number of convolutional and linear layers is at most 1 then the content of the child’s list is appended to the current list.
 2. Otherwise, the whole child’s list is appended as a single element.
- (c) Next, the number of blocks and the number of single layers in the list are computed. A single layer can also be a list containing a single layer. A block is defined as a list containing at least two layers.
- (d) If the computed number of single layers is greater than the number of blocks and we are not in the root of the model, all elements in the list are unpacked

and their contents are appended separately to the resulting list. Otherwise, the list is returned unchanged.

The proposed algorithm is a heuristic and it is possible to construct a counterexample of an architecture which would not be standardized correctly. However, in our tests it performed well and created appropriate basic building blocks.

```

InvertedResidual(
  (conv_pw): Conv2d(...)
  (bn1): BatchNorm2d(...)
  (act1): SiLU(...)
  (conv_dw): Conv2d(...)
  (bn2): BatchNorm2d(...)
  (act2): SiLU(...)
  (se): SqueezeExcite(
    (conv_reduce): Conv2d(...)
    (act1): SiLU(...)
    (conv_expand): Conv2d(...) )
  (conv_pw1): Conv2d(...)
  (bn3): BatchNorm2d(...)
)

```

(a)

```

[Conv2d(...),
 BatchNorm2d(...),
 SiLU(...),
 Conv2d(...),
 BatchNorm2d(...),
 SiLU(...),
 Conv2d(...),
 SiLU(...),
 Conv2d(...),
 Conv2d(...),
 BatchNorm2d(...)]

```

(b)

Figure 4: Inverted Residual block (a) transformed into a list of layers (b)

```

( (conv_stem): Conv2d(...)
  (bn1): BatchNorm2d(...)
  (act1): SiLU(...)
  (blocks): Sequential(
    (0): Sequential(
      (0): Depthwise
        SeparableConv(...)
    )
    (1): Sequential(
      (0): InvertedResidual(...)
      (1): InvertedResidual(...)
    )
    ...
    (3): Sequential(
      (0): InvertedResidual(...)
      (1): InvertedResidual(...)
      (2): InvertedResidual(...)
    )
    ...
  )
  (conv_head): Conv2d(...)
  (bn2): BatchNorm2d(...)
  (act2): SiLU(...)
  (global_pool): AdaptivePool2d(...)
  (classifier): Linear(...) )

```

(a)

```

[
 [Conv2d(...)],
 [BatchNorm2d(...)],
 [SiLU(...)],
 [Layers of
  DepthwiseSeparableConv],
 [Layers of
  InvertedResidual],
 [Layers of
  InvertedResidual],
 ...
 [Layers of
  InvertedResidual],
 [Layers of
  InvertedResidual],
 [Layers of
  InvertedResidual],
 ...
 [Conv2d(...)],
 [BatchNorm2d(...)],
 [SiLU(...)],
 [AdaptiveAvgPool2d(...)],
 [Linear(...)]
]

```

(b)

Figure 5: EfficientNet (a) transformed into a list of lists of layers (b)

```

Data: A module  $M$ , an integer  $d$  - current depth in DFS tree (initially set
to 0)
Result: A list  $L$  containing layers or lists of layers
1 blocks-standardization( $M, d$ ):
2   Let  $L$  be an empty list;
3   if  $M$  is a single layer then
4     |  $L.append(M)$ ;
5     | return  $L$ ;
6   end
7   foreach  $child$  in  $M.children()$  do
8     |  $child_{blocks} = \text{blocks-standardization}(child, d+1)$ ;
9     | if  $depth(child_{blocks}) > 1$  or number of convolutional + number of
10    | linear layers in  $child_{blocks} \leq 1$  then
11    | | foreach  $block$  in  $child_{blocks}$  do
12    | | |  $L.append(block)$ ;
13    | | end
14    | end
15    | else
16    | |  $L.append(child_{blocks})$ ;
17    | end
18  end
19   $n_{blocks} \leftarrow 0$ ;
20   $n_{layers} \leftarrow 0$ ;
21  foreach  $block$  in  $L$  do
22    | if number of layers in  $block > 1$  then
23    | |  $n_{blocks} \leftarrow n_{blocks} + 1$ ;
24    | else
25    | |  $n_{layers} \leftarrow n_{layers} + 1$ ;
26    | end
27  end
28  if  $n_{blocks} < n_{layers}$  and  $d > 0$  then
29    |  $L_{tmp} \leftarrow L$ ;
30    |  $L.clear()$ ;
31    | foreach  $block$  in  $L_{tmp}$  do
32    | | append each element of  $block$  to  $L$ 
33    | end
34  end
35  return  $L$ ;

```

Algorithm 2: Block standardization using DFS. Module denotes a whole model or it's component at any depth. Function $depth()$ returns the maximal nesting level in the list.

3.3.3 Graph Standardization

The most general method of standardization is the execution graph analysis. In this manner, the method can be applied to models from a variety of libraries, as no prior knowledge or assumptions are needed. The structure of such a representation preserves the relations between the individual tensors as well as the operations that link them.

Figure 6: Example graph standardization (neural network for image classification).

A directed graph in figure 6 (plain) can be constructed using any algorithm for traversal. At the same time, it does not provide any information regarding the architecture of the graph and how the various tensors are related to one another. For that reason, we would like to discover the building blocks of the graph. In fact, neural network division can be accomplished in a trivial manner by applying two additional rules to BFS traversal:

- (a) it will encounter operations that merge paths such as: add, multiply, concatenate. Create a token ($block_{idx} \leftarrow node_{idx}$) and propagate it along successive nodes, until we encounter another token.
- (b) out-degree ≥ 2 , indicating that the paths at this node separates. Create a new token and propagate in the analogous manner.

```

Data: A graph  $G$  and a  $root$  node in  $G$ 
Result: A hash-map  $M: node_{idx} \rightarrow block_{idx}$ 
1 graph-standarization( $G, idx_{root}$ ):
2   Let  $Q$  be a queue;
3   Let  $M$  be a hash-map;
4   Let  $P$  be a list of  $\{Add, Mul, Cat\}$ ;
5    $Q.enqueue(idx_{root})$ ;
6   while  $Q$  is not empty do
7      $idx_{root} \leftarrow Q.dequeue()$ ;
8     if  $idx_{root}$  is not in  $M$  then
9        $M[idx_{root}] \leftarrow idx_{root}$ ;      /* create token (first time) */
10    end
11    foreach node  $idx$  in  $G.next\_functions(idx_{root})$  do
12      if  $idx$  is not visited then
13        Visit  $idx$ ;
14        if node  $G.type(idx)$  in  $P$ ;          /* case (a) */
15        or node  $G.out-degree(idx) \geq 2$ ;    /* case (b) */
16        then
17           $M[idx] \leftarrow idx_{root}$ ;      /* create token */
18        else
19           $M[idx] \leftarrow M[idx_{root}]$ ;    /* push token */
20        end
21         $Q.enqueue(idx)$ ;
22      end
23    end
24  end

```

Algorithm 3: Graph standardization using BFS.

After the process is completed, an ordered graph and blocks are obtained as shown in figure 6 (standardized). It works well with popular architectures, however there are some subtle differences between blocks defined by architects and an automated decomposition. The figure 3 illustrates that the graph standardization captures the essence of Unet architectural principles.

3.4 Scoring methods

Scoring methods are used to compare how similar are any tensors from the teacher and student models. They are used by matching functions to determine which layers should be paired.

3.4.1 Shape Score

Shape Score is a simple method for comparing two tensors. It computes similarity based on their shapes. To receive a non-zero score, tensors must belong to the layers of the same type (e.g. both are weights of a 2d convolutional layer). That ensures that their numbers of dimensions are equal. Let T and S be compared teacher’s and student’s tensors respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}
 T\text{'s size: } & t_1 \times t_2 \times \dots \times t_n \\
 S\text{'s size: } & s_1 \times s_2 \times \dots \times s_n \\
 score(S, T) &= \prod_{i=1}^n \min\left(\frac{t_i}{s_i}, \frac{s_i}{t_i}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

For every dimension the function computes:

- (a) what part of the source’s dimension can be transferred to the target’s dimension (when $s_i \geq t_i$)
- (b) what part of the target’s dimension can be filled with unique parameters from the source’s dimension (when $s_i \leq t_i$).

The final score is the product of dimensions’ ratios. It seems reasonable because when the tensors are the same except for one dimension which has a high ratio (e.g. $s_i = 1, t_i = 128, \frac{s_i}{t_i} = \frac{1}{128}$), the tensors are substantially different. The product captures this relation better than, for example, arithmetic mean.

3.4.2 Autoencoder Score

The objective of this method is to produce a generalized version of the score using self-embedding; however it remains unsupervised, since it does not take into account the loss after weights transfer. Additional information such as the position of the tensor within the processing graph and the role it played in that position is considered. This is done by using graph/node embedding.

The pipeline is more complex and requires some additional work before scoring:

- (a) use graph standardization;
- (b) create a triple of embeddings

$$E[node_{idx}] \longrightarrow \{P : \text{position}, S : \text{structure}, N : \text{node}\}$$

for each tensor;

- (c) create a dataset containing embeddings from student and teacher model, and reward the selection of similar embeddings or locations;
- (d) construct a query (prompt) and create a score matrix for matching methods.

Positional embedding: work on a graph based on block relationships; a graph’s connection density is one of the characteristics of the block; we use the FeatherGraph [RS20] algorithm to generate a feature vector for each block.

Structural embedding: work on a graph within block - node relationships; for each node in the block we create node embedding using NetMF [Qiu+18] algorithm.

Node embedding: calculate the shape score between wide and deep abstract tensors: (100, 10, 1, 1), (10, 100, 1, 1); and standardize the original shape vector so that it can be used as an additional feature.

The next step is the definition of the dataset on which the auto-encoder should be trained. Firstly, embeddings are constructed for each of the tensors in the student and teacher model. The $Q(E[node_{src}], E[node_{dst}])$ pairs can be created for tensors belonging to the same model. Labels are assigned according to: same tensor - 1; inside the same block - 0.5; outside - 0. However, it is unclear whether the student’s tensors have any relation with the teacher. We believe that while learning a small shared neural network, in attempt to predict the labels for mutual models, the embeddings between these two separate architectures will be unified.

As an autodecoder model we used a 3-layer network: (125, 50, 25); however, there are likely better architectures for this task, but this topic is beyond the scope of this work. The autoencoder needs the source $node_{src} : \{P_{src}, S_{src}, N_{src}\}$ and the destination $node_{dst} : \{P_{dst}, S_{dst}, N_{dst}\}$ to determine if a given position is appropriate:

$$Q(\{P_{src}, S_{src}, N_{src}\}, \{P_{dst}, S_{dst}, N_{dst}\}) \longrightarrow [0, 1]$$

3.5 Matching methods

Matching methods get the standardized models. Their objective is to generate pairs of teacher’s and student’s layers in such a way that the performance of transfer is high.

3.5.1 Dynamic Programming Flat Matching

This is a basic matching. It requires models to be standardized by a Flatten Standardization. As a result they are represented as a list of layers. The algorithm has been inspired by a dynamic programming algorithm for the Longest Common Subsequence problem [WF74].

Layers in a neural network perform different functions depending on their position. That is why the layers’ positions should be taken into account. The solution of the Longest Common Subsequence problem preserves the order of elements. However, when the model is completely flattened, this constraint should be soft. Let’s consider an example in which a teacher model consists of a convolutional and a batch normalization layer pair repeated twice while a student model has the pair repeated three times. If repeating and returning to previous layers is not allowed then at least one convolutional and one batch normalization layer would not be initialized. In order to initialize all layers with weights from the teacher model, the constraint has to be soft with a penalty for getting back. The

proposed dynamic programming formula is as follows:

$$dp[i, j] = \max \left(dp[i, j-1], dp[i-1, j], \right. \\ \left. \max_{0 \leq k \leq m} dp[i-1, k] + \text{score}(\text{student}_i, \text{teacher}_j) - \text{penalty}(k - j) \right) \\ \text{penalty}(x) = \max \left(\frac{1}{2}(x + 1), 0 \right)$$

where m is the length of the flattened teacher model. At step (i, j) there is considered matching of an i -th layer of the student with an j -th layer of the teacher. The score in this cell is a maximum score of a few possibilities:

- (a) Layers i and j are not matched and the score is equal to the score of the first i layers matched with the first $j - 1$ layers
- (b) Layers i and j are not matched and the score is equal to the score of the first $i - 1$ layers matched with the first j layers.
- (c) Layers i and j are matched and their score is added to the score of the first $i - 1$ layers matched with the first k layers of the teacher. If $k \geq j$ then the return from further layers incurs a penalty.

The penalty is an increasing function - longer returns should receive higher penalties. It is also lower than its positive argument. The maximal score obtained in matching without returns and repetitions from index j to index k in the teacher is equal to $k - j$ (score of matching a pair of tensors is at most 1). If the penalty was greater than its positive argument, it would make no sense to return to previous layers.

At every step, it is remembered which action has been chosen. The final matching score is present in $dp[n, m]$ where n, m are lengths of a student and a teacher models, respectively. Starting from cell (n, m) and following saved actions, it is possible to restore matching with the highest score.

3.5.2 Dynamic Programming Matching

This matching technique is also based on dynamic programming. It requires standardization that divides models into blocks (i.e. Blocks Standardization or Graph Standardization). It works in two separate phases. In the first phase, the similarity of every pair of blocks (clusters) is computed. In the second phase, using the similarities between blocks, the similarity of the models is determined and the blocks are matched. In both phases, models are represented as sequences and for every pair in teacher's and student's sequences, a score is available. In the first phase, the sequences consist of layers present in single blocks and their score is computed with one of the score functions described earlier. In the second phase, sequences consist of blocks and the score for every pair is known from the previous phase.

In both phases, matching is performed using dynamic programming. Below, it is described from the perspective of phase two. To get the description of phase one,

blocks have to be replaced with layers and models have to be replaced with blocks. Cell (i, j) represents the matching of the first i blocks of the student model with the first j blocks of the teacher model. The matching can be created in several ways:

- (a) the j -th block of the teacher is not matched with any block and the matching is equal to the matching at $(i, j - 1)$.
- (b) no teacher's block is assigned to i -th student block, matching is the same as matching at $(i - 1, j)$.
- (c) the teacher's j -th block is matched with every suitable student's block in the range $[k, i]$ and the prefixes of the student of length $k - 1$ and the teacher of length $j - 1$ are matched.

The exact formula can be seen in figure 7. When layer j is assigned to more than one layer the scores are summed. To prevent too long matches, the sum is divided by the square root of the length of the match. It encourages the algorithm to create more diverse matchings. Let's consider a situation when the part of the teacher consists of two blocks t_1, t_2 and the part of the student consists of three blocks s_1, s_2, s_3 and $score(s_i, t_j) = a > 0$ for every $i = 1, 2, 3, j = 1, 2$. Without division all three matchings $[(t_1, s_1), (t_1, s_2), (t_1, s_3)], [(t_2, s_1), (t_2, s_2), (t_2, s_3)], [(t_1, s_1), (t_1, s_2), (t_2, s_3)]$ receive the same score (equal to $3a$) while only the third one uses weights from both teacher's layers. To prevent such situations all matchings with a single source layer have to be done at once and their sum has to be multiplied by some function $f(d)$ where d is the number of matched layers with a single source layer. We want $f(d)$ to be a decreasing function - adding more layers should give a lower score per layer. We also want $d \cdot f(d)$ to be an increasing function - adding more layers should increase the total score. An example of such family of functions is $f(d) = d^{-x}$ for $0 < x < 1$. We have chosen $x = \frac{1}{2}$ that yields $f(d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}}$.

At every step of computations, chosen actions are recorded. The cell $dp[n, m]$ contains the score obtained from the matching of the models, where n, m are the numbers of blocks in the student and the teacher model, respectively. Matching of blocks can be restored by following the actions backward, starting from cell (n, m) . When the blocks' pairs are known, it is possible to match layers within blocks using the information from the first phase of the algorithm.

Figure 7: Dynamic Programming Matching of models' blocks (or layers). Cell (i, j) denotes the matching of student's blocks' prefix of length i with teacher's blocks' prefix of length j . The vertical axis represents the student model while the horizontal represents the teacher. The s_l denotes the l -th block of the student and the t_j denotes the j -th block of the teacher.

3.5.3 Bipartite Matching

Bipartite Matching relies on Dynamic Programming Matching to calculate similarity between blocks (based on layers matching), however, on the block level it is based on the *primal-dual* method for finding a maximum weight matching and the *blossom* method used to find augmenting paths [Gal86].

Each block in teacher and student models can be interpreted as a vertex from two disjoint sets G_1 and G_2 such that every vertex from G_1 is connected to each vertex from G_2 with a weight equal to the similarity measure. In such setup, block matching problem is reducible to maximum weight bipartite matching in polynomial time.

This method utilizes the following score:

$$score = \left(1 - \left(\frac{i_1}{n} - \frac{i_2}{m} \right)^2 \right) * dp_matching_score$$

where i_1 is the index of the block in the teacher architecture and i_2 is that of the student architecture. Taking index into account encourages the algorithm to match blocks at similar stages of the network.

Figure 8: Bipartite graph matching.

3.5.4 Nested Bipartite Matching

Nested Bipartite Matching uses concepts introduced in Bipartite Matching, but also relies on the same maximum weight bipartite matching technique for layer-level matching.

3.5.5 Argmax Matching

The method for each layer in the student model chooses layer in the teacher model it has highest score with. It does not make much sense with Shape Score because then the position in the network is not taken into account. However it should work better with an AutoEncoder Score as it uses the neighborhood of the layer to decide about the score.

3.5.6 Random Matching

This method matches random layers of the same type. Its purpose is to be a baseline. Other methods have to be significantly better than this one to demonstrate that ideas behind them work.

3.6 Transfer methods

The last part of our method is the transfer itself. When the layers are matched, parameters can be transferred from source to target tensors. We match tensors of different shapes (but the same number of dimensions). The transfer method has to determine which parameters to transfer when the size of the source dimension is larger than the size of the target dimension. When the size of the source dimension is smaller than the size of the target dimension it has to choose how and which parts of the target tensor will be filled.

If the layer contains both weights and biases, the mapping between parameters is computed for weights and the same indices are used for biases.

In the description of transfer methods S, T denote the student's and teacher's tensors respectively. Their sizes are as follows: S 's size: $s_1 \times s_2 \times \dots \times s_n$, T 's size: $t_1 \times t_2 \times \dots \times t_n$.

3.6.1 Clip Transfer

This method copies the center crop of T to the center crop of S . For every dimension, it chooses a smaller size and crops the larger size cutting off a beginning and an end of the tensor so that the sizes are equal. When sizes of all dimensions are equal, parameters can be copied from T to S . Let's define a function g .

$$g(j, x, y) = \begin{cases} j + \lfloor \frac{x-y}{2} \rfloor & \text{if } x > y \\ j & \text{if } x \leq y \end{cases}$$

Then the parameters are mapped this way:

$$S_{g(j_1, s_1, t_1), g(j_2, s_2, t_2), \dots, g(j_n, s_n, t_n)} = T_{g(j_1, t_1, s_1), g(j_2, t_2, s_2), \dots, g(j_n, t_n, s_n)}$$

for every $j \in \{1, \dots, \min(s_1, t_1)\} \times \{1, \dots, \min(s_2, t_2)\} \times \dots \times \{1, \dots, \min(s_n, t_n)\}$

Visual representation of this matching can be seen in figure 9. It represents the transfer of parameters from two consecutive layers in the teacher matched to two consecutive layers in the student. The nodes represent neurons in fully connected layers or channels in convolutional layers (in standard convolutional layers every channel in the input is connected with every channel in the output). As for filters in convolutional layers also their centers are mapped. If the filter of size 5×5 is transferred to the filter of size 3×3 , its center crop of size 3×3 is copied to the destination filter. If the filter of size 3×3 is transferred to the filter of size 5×5 , then only the center of the destination filter gets new parameters and the border is left with default initialization.

Clip Transfer has another important property. It preserves the flow of the information from the original network. Let's consider a matching of two consecutive layers from a teacher T_1, T_2 to two consecutive layers in a student S_1, S_2 . Then matched input neurons of T_2 and S_2 correspond to the same output neuron of T_1 . As a result, weights copied from T_2 to S_2 are used to process information from the same source as in T_2 .

This property is also useful when dealing with parallel connections. When values from parallel connections are added, they are added from the same pairs as in the original network.

(a) large to small

(b) small to large

Figure 9: Clip Transfer visualisation between a larger teacher and a smaller student (a) and between a smaller teacher and a larger student (b). Nodes chosen in the first layer are yellow, nodes chosen in the second layer are blue. Output nodes of the first layer and input nodes of the second layer chosen in both layers are half-yellow half-blue

3.6.2 Full Transfer

Full Transfer is an extension of a Clip Transfer. It works in the same way when the size of the source dimension is larger than the size of the target dimension. But when the target dimension is larger, it replicates the weights from the source to fill the target completely. The core that is a center crop is preserved but the beginning and the end are not left with the default initialization but they receive weights from random neurons/channels. For this method, g is defined as follows:

$$g(j, x, y) = \begin{cases} j + \lfloor \frac{x-y}{2} \rfloor & \text{if } x > y \\ j - \lfloor \frac{y-x}{2} \rfloor & \text{if } x \leq y \text{ and } \lfloor \frac{y-x}{2} \rfloor < j \leq y - \lfloor \frac{y-x}{2} \rfloor \\ \text{random value from } \{1, \dots, x\} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then the parameters are mapped this way:

$$S_j = T_{g(j_1, t_1, s_1), g(j_2, t_2, s_2), \dots, g(j_n, t_n, s_n)}$$

for every $j \in \{1, \dots, s_1\} \times \{1, \dots, s_2\} \times \dots \times \{1, \dots, s_n\}$

As a result, every single parameter in S is initialized using data from T but repetitions can occur.

3.6.3 Magnitude Transfer

Magnitude transfer modifies the behavior of Clip Transfer in terms of choosing input and output channels/neurons. Weights at kernel level are transferred in the same way as in Clip Transfer. However, in the dimensions of input and output channels, the algorithm works differently when the size of the source dimension is greater than the size of the target dimension. The top s_i channels/neurons with the greatest L^1 norm of input/output weights are chosen.

The process is performed independently for every pair of tensors. As a consequence, different input and output channels in consecutive layers can be chosen. This situation is presented in the figure 10. When the parameters are transferred, a single neuron in the student (output from S_1 , input to S_2) may correspond to two different neurons from T_1 and T_2 . Thus, the input neuron in S_2 receives different information than it received in T_2 . As a result, the flow of the information is not preserved.

Figure 10: Magnitude Transfer - when the size of the teacher layer is greater than the size of the student layer, neurons/channels with the greatest L^1 norm are chosen. Neurons chosen in the first layer are yellow, neurons chosen in the second layer are blue, neurons chosen in both layers are colored diagonally.

3.6.4 Trace Transfer

To address the problem of the lost information flow in the Magnitude Transfer, the Trace Transfer has been created. It also chooses output channels with the greatest L^1 norm but the input channels are the same as the output channels of the previous layer. The implementation uses the execution graph analysis. The chosen indices are propagated through the network. When the layer is processed, it receives the output channels' indices from the previous layer and selects the output channels (only if the number of output channels in S is smaller than the number of output channels in T , otherwise all channels can be chosen). The output channels are remembered and when another layer takes as input the output of this layer, it receives these channels.

This approach solves the problem for layers connected sequentially but has

problems with parallel connections. When the algorithm traversing the execution graph approaches the addition or multiplication node it has to decide which indices to choose. To make the algorithm deterministic the first input is chosen. Nevertheless, none of the decisions allows to preserve the information flow as values from non-corresponding nodes will be added/multiplied.

Figure 11: Trace Transfer - selected output channels in T_1 are the same as input channels in T_2

3.7 Similarity of architectures

As a by-product of our matching functions the measure of similarity of architectures has been created. While choosing the best matching, we have to score different matching possibilities. As a result, a numerical value representing the quality of the matching is computed. Every student's layer is matched to at most one teacher's layer and the score of the single matching is at most 1. Thus the maximal score of the matching is equal to the number of layers in the student model. In other words, the maximal value of the matching is equal to the matching of student with itself. With this knowledge, we could define a similarity of architectures:

$$f(\text{student}, \text{teacher}) = \frac{\text{score}(\text{student}, \text{teacher})}{\text{score}(\text{student}, \text{student})}$$

The values of this function belong to $[0, 1]$. However, it is not symmetric. To make it symmetric we can take f in both directions and average the results. We decided to choose a geometric mean. Finally, we define similarity between two models a, b as:

$$\text{sim}(a, b) = \sqrt{f(a, b)f(b, a)} = \sqrt{\frac{\text{score}(a, b) \text{score}(b, a)}{\text{score}(a, a) \text{score}(b, b)}}$$

4.1 Datasets

We evaluated our methods on two datasets CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 [Kri12]. Both datasets consist of 60000 32×32 images. Each of them contains 50000 training and 10000 test images. Images in CIFAR-10 belong to 10 different classes and images in CIFAR-100 belong to 100 different classes. For example, classes in CIFAR-10 are the following: airplane, automobile, bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse, ship, truck.

Transfer learning in the form used most widely to this day usually involves transfer from ImageNet [Rus+15] to other domains. ImageNet data can be divided into 1000 classes.

4.2 Architectures

The following architectures have been used during the experimentation process:

- **ResNet** [He+15b] is a convolutional network architecture that utilizes residual connections.
- **EfficientNet** [TL19a] is an architecture aimed at model scaling of all of the dimensions in a balanced manner. Intuitively, such architectures facilitate IAT.
- **UNet** [RFB15] might be relatively difficult for the matching algorithms. UNet is an architecture based on contracting and expanding path that uses the contracting feature vectors to expand the tensor.
- **MobileNet** [How+17] uses depth-wise separable convolutional layers [KGC17] which introduce significant parameter count optimizations while being an equivalent of a standard convolutional layer. In fact, depth-wise separable convolutional layers consist of two smaller convolutional sub-layers.
- **MixNet**³ [TL19b] use mixed depthwise convolution (MixConv) that relies on multiple parallel convolutions with varying kernel sizes in each layer. This causes high-branching with short branches.
- **MnasNet** [Tan+19] was optimized for mobile phones using Mobile Neural Architecture Search reinforcement learning approach. Blocks of the network contain random number of layers of the same type. In addition to that, each layer is a composite and contains multiple basic operations. Types of operations and number of layers in each block are searched.
- **RegNet**³ [Rad+20] is an architecture designed with the help of NAS. RegNetX networks consist of residual bottleneck blocks. RegNetY networks additionally take advantage of squeeze-and-excitation layers.

These architectures introduce a variety of challenges to overcome. We have used implementations of this architectures from the *timm library* [Wig19].

³high branching factor

Additionally, we have used our own implementation of **small ResNets** (designed in the original ResNet paper especially for CIFAR datasets). They consist of an input convolutional layer, $6n$ intermediate convolutional layers divided into three groups with input resolutions 32, 16, 8 respectively, each group containing $2n$ layers and a final linear layer. For every group the number of channels is specified. Layers in the first group have 16 channels, in the second group 32 and in the last group 64 channels. Every such network consist of $6n + 2$ weighted layers. Their names are constructed from the total number of weighted layers. For example, resnet20 includes 6 convolutional layers in every group ($n = 3$) making up 3 residual blocks in every group.

We modify this architecture by changing the width of the network. Let the layers belonging to the first group contain c channels. Then layers in the second group have $2c$ channels and layers in the third group have $4c$ channels. For ResNets described above $c = 16$. We define narrow ResNets as ResNets with $c = 10$ and wide ResNets as ResNets with $c = 24$.

4.3 Environment

Experiments were conducted on the Google Cloud Platform. We used TPUs to speed up the computations. Tensor Processing Units (TPUs) [Jou+17] are application-specific integrated circuits designed to accelerate the training of machine learning models. Their main part is Matrix Multiply Unit that can perform 64K multiply-and-adds per cycle. Every TPU consists of 8 cores. Because of that, a distributed training is necessary. We have implemented it with the help of PyTorch XLA library.

4.4 Implementation Details

For our experiments we had to pretrain a set of models. They were trained using the Adam optimizer [KB14] with initial learning rate 10^{-2} and cosine annealing for learning rate scheduling [LH16]:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{min} + \frac{1}{2}(\eta_{max} - \eta_{min})(1 + \cos(\frac{t}{T_{max}}\pi))$$

with η_{max} being the initial learning rate, $\eta_{min} = 10^{-3}$, $T_{max} = 50$ and t being the current number of epochs. Small ResNets were trained with the batch size of 128 while the other models had the batch size equal to 32. Models were trained for 50 epochs and every training was repeated 5 times to average the training metrics.

Parameters from pretrained models were later transferred to student models. To evaluate the performance of different transfer methods, student models were fine-tuned for 4 epochs with $\eta_{max} = 10^{-3}$, $\eta_{min} = 10^{-4}$, $T_{max} = 50$. Other settings were the same as in pretraining.

After the best method had been chosen, it was used to transfer parameters between more pairs of models. The models were fine-tuned for 20 epochs with the following parameters: $\eta_{max} = 10^{-3}$, $\eta_{min} = 10^{-4}$, $T_{max} = 50$.

5.1 Transfer methods

We describe the methods using the following tuples:

$$(Standardization, Matching, Scoring, Transfer)$$

Then we describe the transfer using:

$$(teacher, student)$$

To measure the IAT performance, the teacher model is trained for 50 epochs, then IAT is applied to (teacher, student). Let $acc(M, I, n)$, be equal to the test accuracy of a model M initialized with I trained for n epochs. Then the performance of an IAT method for a pair (teacher, student) can be expressed as:

$$performance(student, teacher, IAT) = \frac{acc(student, IAT(teacher, student), 4)}{acc(student, Xavier, 4)}$$

The performance of methods on various (teacher, student) pairs is shown in table 1. We measure a mean performance of a method as an arithmetic mean of performances over different pairs. Notice that some values in the table are less than 1. It means that our initialization was worse than the default one. The default initialization is always available and in such cases we can use it. That is why we also compute mean' that is a mean of values clipped to $[1, \infty)$. Let p be the vector (of length m) of performance for a single method over all pairs. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{mean} &= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m p_i \\ \text{mean}' &= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \max(p_i, 1) \end{aligned}$$

There are also some zeros in the table. They appeared there because for given initializations gradient explosion occurred. It would be possible to prevent it by lowering the learning rate but that would influence the training speed for other pairs. Another solution would be to run these cases with different settings but that would make setup inconsistent across the whole experiment. When we think of it differently, we can say that it was the method that initialized the model improperly which caused the gradient explosion. With such logic the zeros are justified.

The problem of zeros is also handled well by the mean' score. The ordering of the methods for both scores is almost the same, so we conclude that these problems do not have much influence on the results.

The (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip) method turned out to be the best and it was used in the later experiments. The (Blocks, DP, AutoEncoder, Clip) method is not much worse, but its second position shows that the AutoEncoder score requires some improvements to become the best scoring function.

The selection of methods may pose some questions as not every possible combination has been tested. The table was created incrementally. At first, all matching methods were tested with all adequate standardization methods (i.e. DPFlat only with Flatten Standardization; DP, Bipartite and NBipartite with Blocks and Graph) with Clip Transfer and Shape Score. DP Matching emerged as the best matching option. This 2-level dynamic programming approach detects and matches structures well. Bipartite matching was second best. It uses the same method to compute similarities between blocks but matches blocks by finding maximal value matching between them. Bipartite matching at the blocks level turns out to be effective. Nevertheless, applying it on both levels (blocks and layers) as NBipartite Matching does not give as good results as the previous methods. In this comparison also Blocks Standardization proved to be superior to Graph Matching. It was able to split the architectures into logical blocks defined by the authors. Blocks produced by Graph Matching are different than blocks proposed by the authors. That can make it difficult to create effective matchings. As expected, DPFlat Matching did not perform well. It does not use the underlying structure of blocks but makes a one-dimensional list of layers from every model. That does not allow to *understand* how the network was build and match its logical components.

After this phase, 2 best combinations were chosen ((Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip), (Blocks, Bipartite, Shape, Clip)) and were tested with other Transfer Methods. However, Clip Transfer proved to still be the best. As previously described, it preserves the flow of the original network. Magnitude and Trace Transfers have difficulties preserving it. On the other hand, Full Transfer repeats weights what turned out not to be beneficial.

Finally, the AutoEncoder score was added and it was evaluated with 2 best combinations so far. In both cases its results were a bit worse than the results of the Shape Score.

Methods were compared also with Random Matching. The mean score of Random Matching is less than 1 and most of our methods have scores greater then 2. It shows that they work and are significantly better than classical initialization methods.

5.2 Comparison to initialization

Figure 12 shows how accuracy and loss changed over iterations of training on *CIFAR100* after various initialization methods being applied to *mnasnet_100* architecture. Every iteration corresponds to a single batch. The batch size in this experiment was 32 so the experiment shows about 3 epochs of training. This experiment was performed in the early stage of research and the used algorithm was similar to (Graph, Argmax, AutoEncoder, Clip). Similarity between

architectures was also computed by this algorithm and that is why it was different than the final similarity metric. $IAT(score = 0.9; CIFAR100)$ series is a moving average of an accuracy of $mnasnet_100$ on $CIFAR100$ after IAT from an architecture with similarity 0.9 to $mnasnet_100$. Similarly, $IAT(score = 0.1; CIFAR100)$ is a moving average of an accuracy of $mnasnet_100$ after IAT from an architecture with similarity equal to 0.1. IAT with $score = 0.1$ and $score = 0.9$ for ImageNet as a source domain is also tested. We compare this against the Xavier and Kaiming initialization accuracy series and crossdomain (ImageNet) same-architecture transfer learning (black series). Bounding boxes around series show batch metric range.

Figure 12: Same domain, cross domain and random initialization comparison. Transfer between architectures of different similarity scores has been used.

We can see how training accuracy after initialization changed over iterations. Our method, when used to transfer knowledge from an architecture of similarity to $mnasnet_100$ equal to 0.9 in the same domain yields better results than crossdomain transfer from $mnasnet_100$ to $mnasnet_100$ (transfer learning from ImageNet). When just the source domain is changed, i.e. we transfer from *ImageNet* to *CIFAR100*, our method performs worse than the classic transfer learning method because it uses architectures of $sim \approx 1$. Transferring from architectures of similarity equal to or less than 0.1 using our method still yields better results than random initialization. In every case, our method has experimentally proven to yield significantly better results than random

initialization.

Figure 13: Transfer between different EfficientNets on CIFAR10 (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip)

Figure 14: Transfer between different EfficientNets on CIFAR100 (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip)

5.3 Transfer inside a single family of models

Intuitively, using IAT inside a single family of models should give high accuracies as similarities are significant.

Figures 13 and 14 show the test accuracy over epochs after transfer for EfficientNet family of architectures. Gray curves mark how student architecture

increases its accuracy when training from scratch. Black dashed lines show the constant value of this accuracy after 50 epochs. Other series show how the accuracy changed when training the student model after transferring from the given teacher.

Note that the accuracies after transfer and fine-tuning for one epoch are a few times greater than the accuracy achieved with default initialization. It means that the knowledge is really moved between models by our method.

Another important observation is that in some cases final accuracies are better than the final accuracy achieved by the model with default initialization even though it was trained for 50 epochs and the number of epochs after the transfer was only 20.

5.4 No train - no gain

Figure 15 shows how accuracy changed when learning after IAT from a teacher model with given number of training epochs. Gray line corresponds to training the student with default initialization.

Teacher models trained on a larger number of epochs constitute for better teachers which was to be expected. Moreover, transfer from a larger model leads to the excess of the final accuracy of a student model trained from scratch.

Figure 15: Accuracy of the student model after a transfer from the teacher model pretrained for different numbers of epochs. The numbers denote the epochs' count. Dataset: CIFAR100, method: (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip)

Figure 16: Accuracy of the EfficientNet-B0 after a transfer from architectures of different similarity with the target model (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip)

5.5 Different similarities

Models of various architectures with different similarities have been used as teachers for EfficientNet-B0 and summarized in figure 16. Table 2 illustrates similarities of architectures used in figure 16 to EfficientNet-B0. The less similar the architecture the worse the results. Despite the models belonging to different families of architectures, the knowledge is still transferred. Training starts with much higher accuracy than in case of the default initialization. That proves that our method can take knowledge from one model and transfer it to the other, independently create model what to our best knowledge have not been done before.

semnasnet_100	0.76
mnasnet_100	0.70
tf_mobilenetv3_large_minimal_100	0.56
mixnet_s	0.51
regnety_004	0.31

Table 2: Similarity of teacher models to the student (EfficientNet-B0) based on DP matching

Note how closely related are MnasNet with SemnasNet on both subfigures and MobileNet with MixNet on (b) subfigure. Even though the similarity for mnasnet

and semnasnet differs just by 0.06 and the similarity for mobilenet and mnasnet by 0.05, the differences in achieved accuracy are not directly proportional to this difference. This shows that there are some nonlinear similarities in the architectures undetected by our similarity metric.

5.6 Small ResNets

Figure 17 shows the test accuracies after the transfer between different small ResNets models. On subfigure (a) we can see transfers to resnet14. The highest accuracy is obtained with weights from resnet20. The deeper (and less similar) the model with resnet14, the worse the accuracy. Subfigure (b) shows similar behavior - networks with similar depths to resnet20 transfer better. On subfigure (c) we can see that the worst accuracy is achieved with weights from resnet14. The resnet14 and resnet32 differ significantly. Nevertheless, the transfer also provides a great improvement compared to the default initialization.

Figure 18 also presents transfer among small ResNets. This time, it is the width that is changing. Weights are transferred to the models of standard width. In both cases, transfer from wider architecture produces better results. For resnet20 both wide networks give better than default initialization. Transfer from narrow networks is not as efficient. They probably had to represent knowledge in a different manner (more compressed) and it is not easily transferable.

Transfer to narrow (a) and wide (b) networks is shown in figure 19. It is worth noting that knowledge between wide and narrow networks does not transfer well. The ratio of their widths is 12 : 5. It probably forces them to represent the knowledge in a considerably different way.

Figure 17: Test accuracy after the transfer between small ResNets on CIFAR10, the networks have varying depths (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip)

Figure 18: Test accuracy after a transfer between small ResNets on CIFAR10, the networks have varying widths, (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip)

Figure 19: Test accuracy after a transfer to small ResNets with low (a) and high (b) number of channels, (Blocks, DP, Shape, Clip)

Figure 20: Matrix of similarity between architectures

5.7 Similarity Matrix

Figure 20 presents proposed similarity between various architectures used in the experiments. Values at the diagonal are equal to one as every model has the maximal similarity with itself. We can see groups of similar architectures. For example, EfficientNets have high similarity between each other. That means that the weights should transfer well between them. We have observed it in the previous experiments. Also, high similarity with other implementations of EfficientNets is

worth noting. Two different implementations of EfficientNet-B0 have similarity equal to 1, $\text{sim}(\text{efficientnet_b0}, \text{tf_efficientnet_b0_ap}) = 1$. That means that our method was able to standardize and match the models properly.

Also, models belonging to the MobileNets family have high similarities among family members. The RegNets are an interesting case. They have low similarities with other models while preserving a quite high similarity inside a family.

5.8 Relation between similarity and transfer performance

We have conducted an experiment to study a relationship between similarity and transfer performance measured as the ratio of accuracy after transfer and 4 epochs of fine-tuning to accuracy after default initialization and 4 epochs of training. We applied transfer to $n = 67$ different transfer pairs. The results can be seen in figure 21. It is visually noticeable that the relationship exists. The higher the similarity, the greater the chance of obtaining high accuracy.

Figure 21: Relationship between similarity and transfer performance. Colors indicate the student model.

We have measured the correlation r between similarity and accuracy ratio.

$$r = 0.83$$

$$r^2 = 0.69$$

The r^2 value indicates that the correlation is strong. We performed a test to test the significance of the correlation coefficient.

Null Hypothesis: $\rho = 0$

Alternate Hypothesis: $\rho \neq 0$

We computed the value of T statistic and the associated p-value:

$$T_{65} = 12$$
$$pvalue \approx 0$$

The p-value is very low. We can reject the Null Hypothesis and conclude that there is a relationship between similarity and accuracy ratio.

Figure 22: Relationship between similarity and transfer performance for specific students. Similar to figure 21, with increasing similarity, gain ratio increases. For some pairs (RegNet as a student), this rule does not apply. It could mean that the similarity score needs improvement, since it cannot reach zero.

This work has succeeded in confirming the following:

1. There is a strong correlation between architecture similarity and quality of transfer. When the architectures are similar, IAT behaves like a transfer learning. If the models are significantly different, it acts like a better initialization method.
2. In all cases, Xavier/Kaiming initialization can be replaced by the presented method by which parameters are transferred between different architectures, as it is more profitable to transfer information from another domain than to teach the model from scratch (figure 12).
3. Our approach demonstrates that kernels can be transferred across different architectures due to their similarity, but it does not replace knowledge distillation, which yields better results. However, it is significantly slower and computationally more intensive than our framework.
4. Similarity measure proposed in this work generally performs decently, but does not handle well all of the cases, as shown in figure 22. Note the RegNet as student IAT performance insignificantly correlated with similarity. Also, note that even though the similarity for mnasnet and semnasnet differs just by 0.06 and the similarity for mobilenet and mixnet by 0.05, the differences in achieved accuracy are not directly proportional to this difference. This shows that there are some nonlinear similarities in the architectures undetected by our similarity metric.
5. The most IAT-friendly family of architectures seems to be EfficientNet family as they were made to address the resources scalability issue by scaling all of the dimensions in a balanced fashion.
6. Unsurprisingly, the more epochs has the teacher model trained for, the better the quality of transfer. It might be the case that the teacher’s knowledge gets less generalized in terms of IAT transfer before overfitting. Such study is out of the scope of this paper.

7.1 IAT in NAS

As shown in figure 21, all IAT methods favour similar architectures. As a consequence, when used in NAS models should not be trained for a constant lower number of iterations before being evaluated. Models should be trained until convergence instead. It should happen much faster thanks to the transferred knowledge. Methods of NAS that utilize local neighbourhood search should give better results. Other methods might be introduced to mitigate this problem.

7.2 Converged accuracy and randomness

Expected quality of the local optimum obtained when training until convergence after IAT in comparison to learning from scratch is yet to be determined. Transferring parameters between layers of differing sizes might introduce some local-optimum bias. Furthermore, adding noise to the transferred parameters might yield different results.

7.3 Normalized initialization

As [GB10] and [He+15c] have shown, the variance of the outputs should be roughly equal to the variance of inputs to avoid vanishing gradients. IAT algorithms presented in this work do not take this information into account, although training has been experimentally proven to be successful.

7.4 Merging layers

Also, some specific cases of merging (transferring from two or more layers to one) or splitting (vice-versa) transfers have to be investigated. Since discrete convolution can be expressed as Toeplitz matrix multiplication consider the following setup:

$$y = W_2 \cdot W_1 \cdot x = W_{21} \cdot x$$

where W_1 and W_2 are toeplitz matrices representing consecutive convolutional layers in a network. If the $W_{21} = W_2 \cdot W_1$ is proven to be a valid Toeplitz matrix representing a convolution, the two layers can be replaced with a single layer. Alternatively, some approximated approach may be used to retrieve convolutional parameters from the W_{21} . Similar matrix multiplication approach can be followed for fully connected layers.

In this section, we discuss the technical crux of the toolkit containing our methods. The code base is open-source under Apache License 2.0, hosted on Github⁴:

<https://github.com/KamilPiechowiak/iatransfer>

The scrum boards for each sprint were hosted on Github Projects. After the completion and delivery of the work, we switch to kanban for prolonged toolkit support. Backlog is modelled using Github Issues.

PyTorch 1.7.1 is the underlying deep-learning framework used in IAT toolkit.

8.1 Design

Figure 23: Abstract entity dependency diagram.

IAT toolkit core was designed using bridge and factory method design patterns. The bridge pattern decouples an abstraction from its implementation classes so the two can vary independently. The necessity of loose coupling between abstract entities appeared as it was desirable to have the ability to use separate algorithms. This way each of the algorithms can be tested on its own or used for further research in any related work but the entire IAT algorithm construction is facilitated. Furthermore, with such loose coupling and type-hinted input/output specification, many dynamic typing and code duplication issues are avoided.

Standardization, transfer and matching methods are logically independent from each other as shown on figure 23 even though matching takes standardized network as an input and transfer takes matched layers. Matching algorithm can not exist without layer scoring algorithm. For reasons mentioned above such tree-like

⁴additional research repository: <https://github.com/maciejczyzewski/tli-pytorch>

architecture (where edges are in fact bridge patterns) is easy to use, test, extend and maintain. Note how this architecture is similar to the star schema used widely in data warehouses.

The ease of extension (also for research purposes) have been described in the following Plugins and Further IAT Research Framework sections.

Figure 24 shows the core UML class diagram. IAT class represents an abstract entity of the entire IAT algorithm that consists of standardization algorithm, matching and transfer.

Figure 24: Simplified UML class diagram.

8.2 API

The basic Python API use-case is shown on figure 25.

```
1  # Given
2  #   pretrained:
3  #       model_from: nn.Module
4  #   instantiated:
5  #       new model_to: nn.Module
6
7  from iatransfer.toolkit import IAT
8
9  # transfer method is initialized by default to our current best
10 # method
11 transfer = IAT()
12
13 transfer(model_from, model_to)
14 # model_to is now initialized with knowledge from model_from
```

Figure 25: Basic API use-case.

8.3 Plugins

IAT factory handles plugins for abstract entities specified in the algorithm - standardization, matching, transfer and scoring.

```
1  from iatransfer.toolkit.base_matching import Matching
2  from iatransfer.toolkit import IAT
3
4  class CustomMatching(Matching):
5      # implement abstract Matching methods
6      # ...
7
8  transfer = IAT(matching='custom')
9  # transfer is now initialized with defaults and CustomMatching
```

Figure 26: Plugin example.

Figure 26 shows how user can introduce new methods to the IAT.

```
1  from iatransfer.toolkit.base_matching import Matching
2  from iatransfer.toolkit import IAT
3
4  class CustomMatching(Matching):
5      def __init__(arg_a, arg_b):
6          # implement custom init
7
8          # implement abstract Matching methods
9          # ...
10
11  transfer = IAT(matching=('custom', {'arg_a': 1, 'arg_b': 2}))
12  # transfer is now initialized with defaults and CustomMatching
13  # initialized with arg_a = 1 and arg_b = 2
```

Figure 27: Custom matching initialized with dictionary of parameters during runtime.

```
1  transfer = IAT(matching=CustomMatching(1, 2))
2  # transfer is now initialized with defaults and CustomMatching
3  # initialized with arg_a = 1 and arg_b = 2
```

Figure 28: Another way to pass parameters.

Figures 27 and 28 show how to parametrize IAT components. The same can be done for any handled component (standardization, matching, scoring, transfer).

8.4 Research Framework

This research used distributed computing and GCP extensively. All experiments conducted might be reproduced using: `iatransfer/research/runner.py`

To research new methods or configurations one can simply add json configuration files to `configs/` directory specifying architectures, algorithms and hyperparameters.

To setup computing instances and TPU on GCP, automated scripts from `scripts/research` can be used.

8.5 Packaging

Software is packaged using python setuptools based custom scripts. As a result of packaging process, two packages are created - toolkit production ready package stripped of research scripts and configurations and the research package that is ready for usage and research reproduction on Google Cloud Platform.

Both can be installed from PyPi index using simple pip commands:

```
pip install iatransfer
```

```
pip install iatransfer_research
```

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Appendix

Figure 29: ResNet on CIFAR100, depth-wise scaling version.

Figure 30: ResNet on CIFAR100, depth and width-wise scaling.

(a) resnet-narrow14

(b) resnet-wide-14

Figure 31: Transfer to ResNet narrow/wide, CIFAR100.

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